

Kinetic Solvent Effect on Hydrolysis of t-Butylchloride in Aqueous Mixtures of some Protic, Aprotic and Dipolar Aprotic Cosolvents in the Light of Initial and Transition State Solvation Energetics

MIRA DATTA (nèe SARKAR) and KIRON K. KUNDU*

Physical Chemistry Laboratories, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 13 April 1993

Kinetic solvent effects (KSE) on a key S_N1 type reaction, such as hydrolysis/solvolysis of t-butylchloride (t-BuCl) in aqueous mixtures of some protic cosolvents, viz. methoxyethanol (ME), ethylene glycol (EG) and glycerol (GL), aprotic cosolvents, viz. 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) and dioxane (D) and dipolar aprotic cosolvents, like *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), have been analysed in the light of solvation energetics of the initial state (IS) and transition state (TS). The required rate constants (k_s) at different temperatures have been determined earlier by conductometric method and the relevant activation parameters by use of the coefficients of the rate constant-temperature equation: $\log k_s = AT^{-1} + B \log T + C$. Transfer energetics of IS and TS from water (w) to other solvents (s) were evaluated by coupling the activation energetics (ΔH^\ddagger) with the previously determined enthalpies of solution ($\Delta \bar{H}_s^0$) of IS: t-BuCl and by coupling the activation free energies (ΔG^\ddagger) with the solvation free energies of the ion-pair $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+}\text{Cl}^-$ – a newly proposed model of the TS: $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+}\dots\text{Cl}^{\delta-}$, as obtained after due correction of the previously determined solvation free energies of the salt $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NHCl}$ in the solvents by an indirect method.

Each of the transfer energetic terms of IS and TS was dissected into cavity, dipole-dipole, dispersion and the rest, hydrophobic-hydrophilic (HH) hydration terms. The latter is the composite contributions of hydrophobic hydration (H_bH) arising from 3(CH₃) groups of partially charged $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+}$ -group and the hydrophilic hydration (H_lH) arising from partially charged $\text{Cl}^{\delta-}$ atom of the TS: $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+}\dots\text{Cl}^{\delta-}$ of t-BuCl. $\Delta\chi_{i,HH}^0(i)$ – and particularly $T\Delta S_{i,HH}^0(i)$ –composition profiles ($X = G, H$ and S and $i = \text{IS}$ or TS) were then analysed in terms of four-step transfer process of Kundu *et al.* and the involved physicochemical properties and especially the relative structuredness of solvents, which guide the HH hydration terms. This helped to understand the observed unique minima in $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ – and hence ΔH^\ddagger –composition profiles in these and other aquo-organic solvents, which proved baffling since the days of the classical work of Ingold and Hughes, so to say on this key S_N1 -type reaction.

Kinetic solvent effects (KSE) of a key S_N1 -type reaction, namely, hydrolysis/solvolysis of tert-butylchloride (t-BuCl) in different media were long since rationalised in the light of general parameters such as ‘solvent polarity’ which sums up all the specific and non-specific interactions of the media with the initial and transition states. Unfortunately, a quantitative measure of this property is always empirical. Consequently, a large number of solvent polarity scales are available¹⁻³. Moreover, such data for mixed solvents are scanty and are quite difficult to assess on the basis of the values of pure solvents.

Since the pioneering work of Leffler and Grunwald⁴, Arnett *et al.*⁵, Abraham⁶ and Parkar *et al.*⁷, increasing efforts⁸⁻¹³ were being made to rationalise the KSE on these types of reactions from a thermodynamic approach. These essentially entailed determining the KSE by splitting the activation parameters into contributions from initial state (IS) to transition state (TS) and hence attempting to correlate and to understand their behaviour in the light of the relevant physicochemical properties of the solvents. Thus, the kinetic characteristics of a reaction can be correlated with or even predicted from the

thermodynamic properties of reacting species. Despite extensive studies of the KSE on S_N1 -type solvolytic reaction of t-BuCl in different aquo-organic solvents^{4-8,14-16}, understanding of KSE from the angle of IS and TS solvation yet remains largely unsolved. This is chiefly because solvation data for the IS and TS were hard to gather due to its rapid hydrolysis in aquo-organic solvents.

Consequent to that, another approach had been explored by evolving the relationship between structure, mechanism and the accompanying 'solvent reorganisation' attending the activation process for this solvolytic reaction. Thus, it has been suggested from the work of Winstein *et al.*¹⁴, Robertson and Sugamri¹⁵, Arnett *et al.*⁵ and Huq¹⁶, among many others, that the evidence of 'solvent reorganisation' was likely to be apparent in ΔH^\ddagger and $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ than in ΔG^\ddagger . While this is undoubtedly true, the work of Robertson and Sugamri¹⁵ proved that for hydrolysis in water and aquo-organic solvents ΔC_p^\ddagger was a more sensitive indicator of solvent reorganisation than ΔH^\ddagger or ΔS^\ddagger . But as the authors themselves indicated, one of the preconditions of using $\partial\Delta C_p^\ddagger$ ($=_s\Delta C_p^\ddagger -_w\Delta C_p^\ddagger$) as the structural indicator is that the primary rate constant (k_s) data must be extremely precise, as after all, ΔC_p^\ddagger is the second temperature derivative of $\log k_s$. Moreover, a careful analysis of relative 'solvent reorganisation' round the IS and TS of t-BuCl seems to reveal that it can hardly be taken as really enlightening as to the observed unique 'endothermic minima' in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger composition profiles, irrespective of the nature of the cosolvents. Also, the variation of $\partial\Delta C_p^\ddagger$ -composition profiles can hardly be taken as that useful as structural probes for those aquo-organic cosolvent systems which are neither strong 3D-structure markers^{9,17} nor 3D-structure breakers^{9,17} but are in the borderline of the two types of cosolvents, such as ethylene glycol (EG)^{18a-b}, glycerol^{18c-c} or cosolvents which have the propensities of forming intercomponent H-bonded complexes, like dioxane^{18f-1}, methoxyethanol (ME)^{18j,k}, 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME)^{18h,b}, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF)^{18m} and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO)^{18n,o} etc.

On the contrary, it is gratifying to note that our present day knowledge on the single ion solvation energetics, especially ΔG_{solv}^0 , based on the most reasonable and widely used tetra-phenylarsonium tetraphenylborate (TATB) reference electrolyte assumption^{19,20} as well as the solvating characteristics and the structuredness of various aquo-organic solvents and especially the above-noted ones^{18a-r}, has attained a spectacular advancement during the last one or two decades. So, it should be considered particularly interesting and useful to make an attempt to see the KSE of t-BuCl in the above-noted aquo-organic solvent systems in the light of IS and TS solvation attainable by indirect but reasonable ways if necessary, because of apparent difficulties of attaining the solvating energetics of IS or TS or both from direct experiments.

As a part of comprehensive studies on the KSE of hydrolysis/solvolytic reaction of t-BuCl in the above-noted aquo-organic solvents, we have recently²¹ determined the rate constants (k_s) of the reaction at different temperatures and evolved the related activation parameters. Moreover, we have studied^{21,22} the heats of solvation of IS : t-BuCl in most of those aqueous cosolvents as well as ethanol (EtOH) and tert-butanol (t-BuOH) or TBA, by a rapid response titration calorimeter (TRONAC model 458). Also, as free energies of solution of t-BuCl are not determinable from direct solubility or vapour pressure measurements due to rapid hydrolysis, we studied^{21,23} also the free energies of solution ΔG_s^0 of the salt $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NHCl}$ in those solvents in order to use its ion-pair as a suitable model of the transition state TS : $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+} \dots \text{Cl}^{\delta-}$. In fact, this salt because of its 3(CH₃) groups, instead of 4(CH₃) groups of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$ salt used by Arnett *et al.*⁵ in aqueous ethanol and by Abraham *et al.*^{3b,24} in some pure nonaqueous solvents, was considered to be the nearest analogue of the transient TS species.

Transfer energetics of IS and TS from water (w) to other solvents (s) were evaluated by coupling the activation enthalpies (ΔH^\ddagger) with the enthalpies of solution ($\Delta \bar{H}_s^0$) of IS : t-BuCl so determined and by coupling the activation free energies (ΔG^\ddagger) with the solvation free energies of the ion-pair

$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NH}^+\text{Cl}^-$ – the proposed model of the TS. In the present paper, we present a review of the said work especially highlighting how the relative contributions of transfer entropies of IS and TS, as guided by hydrophobic hydration (H_bH) effect of hydrophobic $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}^{\delta+}$ and hydrophilic hydration (H_lH) effect of hydrophilic $\text{Cl}^{\delta-}$ of t-BuCl as well as the structuredness of aqueous cosolvents, help reflect the genesis of endothermic minima in $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ and hence in ΔH^\ddagger –composition profiles of the reaction irrespective of the nature of the cosolvents, which proved to be a baffling problem so to say, for long since.

In fact, as indicated earlier, we have determined the rate constants (k_s) of the hydrolysis of t-BuCl in aqueous mixtures of 10, 30, 50 and 70 wt % of the cosolvents from conductance measurement at five equidistant temperatures ranging from 5 to 25°. The values of k_s at different temperatures were fitted into equation (1),

$$\log_{10} k_s = AT^{-1} + B + C \log_{10} T \quad (1)$$

by least-squares and the values of the related activation parameters, viz. ΔG^\ddagger , $T\Delta S^\ddagger$, and ΔH^\ddagger were evaluated at 15° and 25° using the coefficients A , B and C derived thereof. The data at 25° are presented

TABLE I—COEFFICIENTS OF EQN. (1) : $\log_{10} k_s = AT^{-1} + B \log_{10} T + C$ AND THE RELATED ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE HYDROLYSIS OF t-BuCl IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 25°

Cosolvent wt %	A K	B	C	ΔG^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	$T\Delta S^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹
EG-water						
0	-6 318.46	-9.667 7	43.535	19.607	2.981	22.588
10	3 494.48	62.207 1	167.488	19.963	0.298	20 261
30	-124 465.63	-161.133 2	478 687	20.297	-4 512	15 785
50	-15 605.38	-84.471 2	260.179	20.751	-0.342	20,409
70	4 767.20	76.682 5	-208.848	21.700	1.327	23 027
GL-water						
10	-4 990.53	-322.01	945.907	19 871	-5.395	14 487
30	-48 927.71	-352.17	1 033.619	20.070	-5.456	14.628
50	19 198.94	195.01	-549 03	20.310	6.797	27 099
70	-53 468.87	-373.08	1 099.94	20.954	2.097	23.051
ME-water						
10	-46 699.04	-336.22	986 641	20 119	-6.231	13 888
30	-26 931.75	-179.89	533.098	20.665	-4.621	16 094
50	16 194.37	168.41	-474.201	21.764	3.339	25.113
70	16 237.42	164.13	-464.442	22.719	-0.358	22 361
DME-water						
10	-8 775.05	-34.269	112.267	20.128	-0.864	19.264
30	-11 371.37	-54.989	171.598	21.012	-2.146	18 866
50	-664 468.75	-497.581	1 450.240	22 814	-4.530	18 282
70	-7 695.31	-20.846	72.619	23.965	-1 700	22.265
D-water						
10	-44 115.72	-317.332	931 212	20.141	-6.887	13.254
30	-6 243.99	-15.171	55.880	21.004	-2.027	18 977
50	-17 872.38	-107.695	322.843	22.343	-4.965	11 378
70	-1 102.33	25.663	-64.424	23.756	-4.100	19.656
DMSO-water						
10	-17 693.13	-105 340	318.136	19.994	-2.027	17.967
30	-4 440.99	-0.316	13.372	20 599	-1.073	19.526
50	-22 454 98	-143.322	426 930	21.583	-4.353	17 230
70	-11 586 86	-52.998	165.697	23.327	-2.296	21.031
DME-water						
10	10 268.91	121 350	-336.543	19.946	4.382	24.328
30	-38 100.29	-267.813	787.937	20.916	-5.844	15.072
50	-171 211.50	-1 336 349	2 874.940	22 282	-3.071	19 211
70	3 312.50	62.331	-169.359	22.931	-1.759	21 172

in Table I and the composition profiles of ΔG^\ddagger , $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ and ΔH^\ddagger relative to those in water at 15° are presented in Figs. 1(A-H).

system increase monotonically, ΔH^\ddagger -composition profiles exhibit endothermic minima and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ profiles a mirror-image relationship with ΔH^\ddagger -profiles and

Fig. 1(A-D) Variation of the activation parameters (o) ΔG^\ddagger , (Δ) ΔH^\ddagger and (\square) $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ with mol. fraction of water for hydrolysis of t-BuCl in different aquo-organic solvents at 288.15K.

Fig. 1(E-H) Variation of the activation parameters (o) ΔG^\ddagger , (Δ) ΔH^\ddagger and (\square) $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ with mol. fraction of water for hydrolysis of t-BuCl in different aquo-organic solvents at 288.15K.

Fig. 2(a) Variation of $\Delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ of hydrolysis of t-BuCl with X_{H_2O} in different aquo-organic cosolvents at 288.15K

Fig. 2(b) A comparative view of the ΔG^\ddagger -composition profiles of hydrolysis of t-BuCl at 288.15K in aqueous mixtures of similar types of cosolvents.

A perusal of the plots in Fig. 1(A-H) indicates that while ΔG^\ddagger -composition profiles in all the cosolvent

hence the compensation effect. The results thus

reflect that in all the cosolvent systems the rates of the reaction get diminished monotonically with cosolvent compositions, while the observed endothermic minima irrespective of the nature of the cosolvents invariably result from decreased entropy of activation with a minima at the same composition

in the respective cosolvent systems. Evidently some common factors are considered to be the cause of this unique behaviour. Furthermore, a comparison of $\partial\Delta G^\ddagger$ -composition profiles (Fig. 2) indicates that the rates of the reaction decrease monotonically and at any composition the order of the

TABLE 2—VALUES (kJ mol⁻¹) OF ΔG_i^\ddagger (MTS) FROM ΔG_i^\ddagger (Me₃NHCl) AND THE RELEVANT TRANSFER QUANTITIES AS PER EQUATION^c AND $\delta\Delta G^\ddagger$ AND ΔG_i^\ddagger (IS)^e AT 298.15⁺

Cosolvent wt %	ΔG_i^\ddagger (CA) ^a	ΔG_{iB}^\ddagger (C ⁺)	ΔG_{iA}^\ddagger (A ⁻)	ΔG_{iid}^\ddagger (C ⁺)	ΔG_{iid}^\ddagger (A ⁻)	ΔG_{idd}^\ddagger (TS) ^b	$\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (C ⁺)	$\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (A ⁻)	$\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (TS) ^b	ΔG_i^\ddagger (MTS) ^c	$\Delta G_i^{\ddagger d}$	ΔG_i^\ddagger (IS)
TBA-H ₂ O												
10	2.14	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.1	1.2	-2.1	-1.0	-1.4	3.8	0.97	2.8
20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	(6.2)	3.27	2.9
30	4.23	1.5	2.4	0.3	0.6	4.9	-6.2	-5.1	-4.7	8.9	9.28	-0.4
50	6.88	3.8	5.9	0.6	1.2	10.9	-12.5	-6.3	-9.0	16.1	14.60	1.5
EG-H ₂ O												
10	3.90	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	1.3	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	5.0	1.45	3.5
30	8.98	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.5	6.7	-1.3	-0.7	-0.9	15.1	2.86	12.2
50	15.08	0.8	1.2	0.4	1.0	18.2	-2.2	-1.3	-1.7	31.7	4.77	26.9
GL-H ₂ O												
10	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.4	-0.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.4	1.13	-0.7
30	2.63	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.3	2.9	-0.9	-0.6	-0.7	4.9	1.94	2.9
50	5.76	0.7	1.1	0.2	0.6	10.4	-1.8	-1.1	-1.4	15.1	2.94	12.1
ME-H ₂ O												
10	6.21	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	1.4	-0.4	-0.2	-0.3	9.3	2.14	7.2
30	20.78	0.7	1.1	0.3	0.5	5.5	3.4	1.5	3.6	22.1	4.43	17.7
50	36.10	1.8	2.8	0.5	1.1	13.3	-2.9	-1.7	-2.2	45.6	9.02	36.6
DME-H ₂ O												
10	12.45	-0.5	-0.7	0.1	0.1	1.0	-2.0	-1.0	-1.4	16.3	2.18	13.7
30	31.18	-0.5	-0.8	0.2	0.5	4.0	-6.1	-3.0	-4.4	40.5	5.86	34.6
50	55.43	1.8	2.9	0.5	1.0	9.2	-11.2	-5.6	-8.1	67.2	13.41	53.8
D-H ₂ O												
10	9.02	0.4	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.1	-1.9	-1.0	-1.0	9.9	2.23	7.7
30	31.05	1.6	2.5	0.1	0.3	0.4	-5.7	-2.8	-4.1	31.4	5.84	25.6
50	44.80	4.1	6.3	0.3	0.5	0.9	-10.4	-5.2	-7.5	42.6	11.44	31.2
DMSO-H ₂ O												
10	5.98	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.5	0.4	0.1	0.2	-2.6	1.62	-4.2
30	19.66	0.05	0.1	-0.5	-0.4	-22.5	2.1	0.9	1.4	-3.7	4.15	-7.8
50	38.37	0.1	0.2	-1.0	-0.9	-25.9	4.0	1.6	2.7	11.2	0.27	2.9
DME-H ₂ O												
10	9.23	0.1	0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-8.2	-0.4	-0.2	-0.3	1.5	1.42	0.1
30	28.66	0.3	0.4	-0.4	-0.6	-18.4	-1.4	0.8	-1.05	10.1	5.47	4.5
50	48.26	0.7	1.1	-1.0	-1.2	-16.5	-11.8	-1.4	-1.8	43.6	11.19	32.4

^a ΔG_i^\ddagger (CA) denotes ΔG_i^\ddagger (Me₃NHCl) with C⁺ = Me₃NH⁺ and A⁻ = Cl⁻

^b ΔG_i^\ddagger (TS) denotes ΔG_i^\ddagger (transition state of t-BuCl), i.e. ΔG_i^\ddagger (Me₃C^{δ+}.....Cl^{δ-})

ΔG_i^\ddagger (MTS) = ΔG_i^\ddagger (Me₃NHCl) - $\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (Me₃NH⁺ + Cl⁻) + $\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (Me₃C^{δ+}.....Cl^{δ-}) - ΔG_{iB}^\ddagger (Me₃NH⁺ + Cl⁻) - ΔG_{iid}^\ddagger (Me₃NH⁺ + Cl⁻) + ΔG_{idd}^\ddagger (Me₃C^{δ+}.....Cl^{δ-}) (vide equation 3).

^cthe relevant parameter for the computation of cavity effect $\Delta G_{i,cav}^\ddagger$ (i), Born type electrostatic ΔG_{iB}^\ddagger (i) ion-dipole ΔG_{iid}^\ddagger (i) and dipole-dipole interaction of transition state ΔG_{idd}^\ddagger (TS) as per appropriate equations in Refs. 20-23, 25.

^dVide Ref. 23. ^e $\delta\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta G_i^\ddagger$ (MTS) - ΔG_i^\ddagger (IS).

decrement is DME > D > ME ≈ DMF > DMSO > EG > GL > W. Also, in the similar series of cosolvents the order is EtOH (Ref. 5) > EG > GL, DME > ME > EG, THF > DME > D and DMF > DMSO > ACN (Ref. 5).

As indicated earlier, an attempt for explaining the genesis of these relative orders in ΔG^\ddagger , minima in $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ and hence the unique endothermic minimum in ΔH^\ddagger irrespective of the nature of the cosolvents boils down to the need of dissecting the activation parameters into the IS and TS contributions and explaining the same in the light of their behaviour as guided by physicochemical properties of the species, solvating characteristics as well as the relative structuredness of solvents. With that objective in view, as indicated earlier, we have determined^{21,22} the partial molar heats of solution ΔH_s^\ddagger of the initial state IS : t-BuCl in most of the aquo-organic solvents, excluding GL but including EtOH as well as t-BuOH, by use of a rapid response Tronac Isoperibol Titration Calorimeter (Model 458). The instrument helped obtain the same by measuring heat changes recorded within 5–10 s of the addition of the substrate, t-BuCl, i.e. well before the onset of hydrolysis of the same. In fact, the method was very similar to that of the Arnett *et al.* for the same in aqueous EtOH⁵. The present results in aqueous EtOH compare fairly well with those of Arnett *et al.* (vide Ref. 22) with a characteristic maxima around the same EtOH composition. It is also gratifying to note that the ΔH_s^\ddagger (IS) thus obtained in different aquo-organic solvent systems on extrapolation to zero composition of the organic cosolvents, led to a common value for that of water ($w\Delta H_s^\ddagger$), which is equal to 6.27 ± 0.25 kJ mol⁻¹ and which could not be determined by direct measurements because of the overlapping of very rapid hydrolysis effect of t-BuCl in pure water. This value helped compute transfer enthalpies of IS : ΔH_t^\ddagger (IS) [= ${}_s\Delta H_s^\ddagger$ (IS) - $w\Delta H_s^\ddagger$ (IS)] and hence of TS, ΔH_t^\ddagger (TS) [= $\partial\Delta H^\ddagger$ - ΔH_t^\ddagger (IS)] in all these aquo-organic solvents. Values of ΔH_t^\ddagger (IS) and ΔH_t^\ddagger (TS) are presented in Tables 4 and 5. A comparative view of the composition profiles of

ΔH^\ddagger (IS) as well as ΔH^\ddagger and ΔH_t^\ddagger (TS) in all the solvent systems reflects that while the variation of ΔH^\ddagger (IS) values is guided by complex structural and interaction effects ΔH_t^\ddagger (IS) values are fairly small as compared to $\partial\Delta H^\ddagger$ values in the respective solvent systems. Evidently $\partial\Delta H^\ddagger$ values are guided by the contributions of ΔH_t^\ddagger of TS rather than that of IS, contrary to what has been concluded by Arnett *et al.*⁵ from the corresponding studies only in aqueous ethanol system.

Moreover, since the enthalpy terms are the sum of the corresponding free energy and entropy terms and since the latter term rather enthalpy term, is a better indicator of solvent structural effects⁵, it is difficult to understand enthalpy terms unambiguously in terms of solvent structural effects unless free energy terms and hence the corresponding terms are available. That is why, as indicated earlier, we have determined^{21,23a} the transfer free energies of the salt (CH₃)₃NHCl, which on due correction yielded ΔG_t^\ddagger values for the ion-pair : (CH₃)₃NH⁺Cl⁻ a nearest analogue of the highly polar TS : Me₃C^{δ+}Cl^{δ-}. But in view of the fact that the salt (CH₃)₃NHCl is highly soluble in most of the aquo-organic solvents, the transfer free energies of the salt were determined by measuring the solubilities of a sparingly soluble salt Me₃NHPh₄ (Ph = phenyl) in the solvents at 25° and by using the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NHCl}) = \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NHPh}_4) - \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-) + \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Cl}^-) \quad (2)$$

The required individual ion contributions for the solvents based on the TATB reference electrolyte assumption were obtained from previous studies^{18a-r}. The values so obtained are presented in Table 3. And these data in fact helped determine the corresponding data of the ion-pair (CH₃)₃NH⁺Cl⁻ which were taken to be suitable model of the transition state (MTS) of t-BuCl = (CH₃)₃C^{δ+}...Cl^{δ-} using the tentative relation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{MTS}) &= \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NH}^+ + \text{Cl}^-) - \Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NH}^+ + \text{Cl}^-) \\ &+ \Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{C}^{\delta+} \dots \text{Cl}^{\delta-}) - \Delta G_{t,\text{Bom}}^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NH}^+ + \text{Cl}^-) \\ &- \Delta G_{t,\text{id}}^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{NH}^+ + \text{Cl}^-) + \Delta G_{t,\text{dd}}^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{C}^{\delta+} \dots \text{Cl}^{\delta-}) \\ &= \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{Me}_3\text{C}^{\delta+} \dots \text{Cl}^{\delta-}) \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where the terms have usual significance^{25,21,23b}. The subscripts cav, B, id and dd refer to the transfer free energy term due to involved cavity, Born type electrostatic ion-dipole and dipole-dipole interaction effects respectively. The corresponding ion-induced dipole interaction terms and the difference in dispersion (disp) interaction terms between the ions of the salt and the ion-pair being likely to be fairly small, have been neglected. Each of the terms was tentatively computed²¹ by the appropriate expressions²⁰ and the required data taken from literature^{20,25}. The values so obtained are presented

in Table 2. These data then helped compute ΔG_i^0 (IS) from the corresponding values of $\partial \Delta G^\ddagger$ in the respective solvent systems. The values of ΔG_i^0 (TS) and ΔG_i^0 (IS) (Table 3) when coupled with the corresponding values of ΔH_i^0 (TS) and H_i^0 (IS) determined earlier²², yielded the desired $T\Delta S_i^0$ (TS) and $T\Delta S_i^0$ values in the solvents concerned. All these values are presented in Tables 4–5.

In order to help understand the behaviour ΔX_i^0 (i) of IS- and TS-composition profiles, attempts

TABLE 3— VALUES (kJ mol⁻¹) OF ΔG_i^0 , $\Delta G_{i,cav}^0$, $\Delta G_{i,dd}^0$, $\Delta G_{i,disp}^0$, $\Delta G_{i,HH}^0$ OF INITIAL STATE (IS) AND TRANSITION STATE (TS/MTS) IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF DIFFERENT COSOLVENTS AT 298.15 K

Cosolvent wt%	cosolvent mol %	ΔG_i^0 (IS)	$\Delta G_{i,cav}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta G_{i,dd}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta G_{i,disp}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta G_{i,HH}^0$ (IS)	ΔG_i^0 (MS)	$\Delta G_{i,cav}^0$ (TS)	$\Delta G_{i,dd}^0$ (TS)	$\Delta G_{i,disp}^0$ (TS)	$\Delta G_{i,m}^0$ (TS)
TBA-H ₂ O											
10	2.6	2.8	-1.3	0.1	-3.7	7.8	3.8	-1.5	1.2	-3.5	7.6
20	5.7	2.9	-4.3	0.3	-6.7	13.6	(6.2)	-4.7	2.8	-6.3	14.4
30	9.6	-0.4	-4.2	0.5	-9.2	12.5	8.9	-4.7	4.9	-8.7	17.4
50	19.5	1.5	-8.2	1.0	-9.7	18.4	16.1	-9.1	10.9	-9.3	23.6
EG-H ₂ O											
10	3.2	3.5	-0.1	0.1	2.9	6.4	5.0	-0.1	1.3	2.7	6.5
30	11.1	12.2	-0.8	0.7	-7.4	19.7	15.1	-0.9	6.7	-6.9	16.2
50	22.5	26.9	-1.6	1.8	-9.3	36.0	31.7	-1.7	18.3	-8.8	23.9
GL-H ₂ O											
10	2.4	-0.7	-0.2	0.0	-3.0	2.5	0.4	-0.2	0.4	-2.8	3.0
30	7.7	2.9	-0.6	0.3	-7.3	10.5	4.9	-0.7	2.9	-6.9	9.6
50	16.4	12.1	-1.3	1.0	-10.3	22.7	15.1	-1.4	10.4	-9.8	15.9
ME-H ₂ O											
10	2.6	7.2	-0.3	0.1	-2.5	9.9	9.3	-0.3	1.4	-2.3	10.5
30	9.2	17.7	3.2	0.5	-6.7	20.7	22.1	3.55	5.5	-6.3	19.3
50	19.2	36.6	-2.0	1.3	-6.9	44.2	45.6	-2.2	13.3	-6.8	41.3
DME-H ₂ O											
10	2.2	13.9	-1.3	0.1	-3.3	18.4	16.1	-1.4	1.0	-3.1	19.8
30	7.9	34.6	-4.0	0.4	-8.4	46.6	40.5	-4.4	4.0	-7.9	48.8
50	16.7	53.8	-7.3	0.9	-10.1	70.3	67.2	-8.1	9.2	-9.7	75.8
D-H ₂ O											
10	2.2	7.7	-0.8	0.0	-3.7	12.2	9.9	-0.9	0.1	-3.4	14.1
30	80.1	25.6	-3.7	0.1	-10.0	39.2	31.4	-4.1	0.4	-9.3	44.4
50	17.0	31.2	-6.8	0.1	-13.2	51.1	42.6	-7.5	0.9	-12.5	61.7
DMSO-H ₂ O											
10	2.4	-4.2	0.2	-0.8	-2.5	-1.1	-2.6	0.2	-8.5	-2.3	8.0
30	9.0	-7.8	1.3	-2.0	-6.9	-0.2	-3.7	1.4	-22.5	-6.5	23.9
50	18.7	2.9	2.4	-2.2	-9.0	11.7	11.2	2.7	-25.9	-9.6	44.0
DMF-H ₂ O											
10	2.7	0.1	-0.3	-0.7	-2.9	4.0	1.5	-0.3	-8.2	-2.7	12.7
30	9.5	4.6	-1.0	-1.6	-7.1	14.3	10.1	-1.1	-18.4	-6.7	36.3
50	19.8	32.4	-1.7	-1.3	-8.6	44.0	43.6	-1.8	-16.5	-8.3	70.2

The relevant parameters for computation of ΔG_i^0 terms for cavity, dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions as per equations in Refs., 20–23 and 25.

TABLE 4- VALUES (kJ mol⁻¹) OF ΔH_i° , $\Delta H_{i,cav}^\circ$, $\Delta H_{i,dd}^\circ$, $\Delta H_{i,disp}^\circ$, $\Delta H_{i,HH}^\circ$, ΔG_i° , ΔS_i° , $\Delta G_{i,HH}^\circ$, $T\Delta S_{i,HH}^\circ$ OF INITIAL STATE (IS) OF t-BuCl IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 298.15 K

Cosol-vent wt%	Cosol-vent mol ⁻¹	ΔH_i° (IS)	$\Delta H_{i,cav}^\circ$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{i,dd}^\circ$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{i,disp}^\circ$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{i,HH}^\circ$ (IS)	ΔG_i° (IS)	$T\Delta S_i^\circ$ (IS)	$\Delta G_{i,HH}^\circ$ (IS)	$T\Delta S_{i,HH}^\circ$ (IS)
TBA-H ₂ O										
10	2.6	3.21	1.5	0.2	-4.1	5.6	2.8	0.4	7.8	-2.2
20	5.7	5.14	5.1	0.5	-8.5	8.0	2.9	2.2	13.6	-5.6
30	9.6	1.51	8.7	0.9	-13.0	4.9	-0.4	1.9	12.5	-7.6
50	19.5	-3.22	8.6	2.1	-16.2	2.3	1.5	-4.7	18.4	-16.1
EG-H ₂ O										
10	3.2	-0.64	1.0	0.3	-3.1	1.2	3.5	-4.1	6.4	-5.2
30	11.1	-1.26	3.7	1.3	-8.9	2.6	12.2	-13.5	19.7	-17.1
50	22.5	-2.82	6.5	3.4	-12.8	0.1	26.9	-29.7	36.0	-35.9
MG-H ₂ O										
10	2.6	-2.30	2.8	0.3	-2.8	-2.6	7.2	-9.5	9.9	-12.5
30	9.2	-3.97	11.4	1.0	-9.0	-7.4	17.7	-21.7	20.7	-28.1
50	19.2	-5.29	10.7	2.5	-11.0	-7.5	36.6	-41.9	44.2	-51.7
DME-H ₂ O										
10	2.2	-2.48	1.4	0.2	-3.3	-0.8	13.9	-16.4	18.4	-19.2
30	7.9	-5.80	5.6	0.8	-10.8	-1.4	34.6	-40.4	46.6	-48.0
50	16.7	-5.63	9.0	1.7	-16.1	-0.2	53.8	-59.4	70.3	-70.5
D-H ₂ O										
10	2.2	-1.63	2.9	0.0	-4.2	-0.3	7.7	-9.3	12.2	-12.5
30	8.1	-5.10	6.5	0.1	-13.1	1.4	25.6	-30.7	39.2	-37.8
50	17.0	-5.95	6.9	0.2	-19.1	6.1	31.2	-37.1	51.1	-45.0
DMSO-H ₂ O										
10	2.4	-2.17	-0.8	-1.5	-2.6	2.7	-4.2	2.0	-1.1	3.8
30	9.0	-2.72	4.5	-4.3	-8.1	5.2	-7.8	5.1	-0.2	5.4
50	18.7	-1.63	12.3	-5.6	-12.9	4.6	2.9	-4.5	11.7	-7.1
DMF-H ₂ O										
10	2.7	-2.94	2.3	-1.5	-3.3	-0.4	0.1	-3.0	4.0	-4.4
30	9.5	-3.30	6.7	-3.8	-9.2	3.0	4.6	-7.9	14.3	-11.3
50	19.8	-1.55	14.7	-4.4	-14.6	2.8	32.4	-33.9	44.0	-41.2

$\Delta H_{i,HH}^\circ$ (IS) = ΔH_i° (IS) - $\Delta H_{i,cav}^\circ$ (IS) - $\Delta H_{i,dd}^\circ$ (IS) - $\Delta H_{i,disp}^\circ$ (IS), where IS stands for initial state of t-BuCl. The relevant parameters for computation of ΔH_i° (IS) terms for cavity, dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions as per equations in Refs. 20-23 and 25

have been made to evaluate the respective contributions of cavity (cav), dipole-dipole (dd), dipole-induced dipole (d-id) and dispersion (disp) interaction effects, whence the rest gave the composite contributions of hydrophobic hydration (H_bH) and hydrophilic hydration (H_lH), termed as HH interactions. While the former H_bH interaction is associated with the hydrophobic hydration of the partially changed hydrophobic part of t-BuCl or its TS, the latter H_lH interaction is associated with the solvent effect on the partially charged hydrophilic Cl^{δ-}. Thus,

$$\Delta X_{i,HH}^\circ(i) = \Delta X_i^\circ(i) - \Delta X_{i,cav}^\circ(i) - \Delta X_{i,dd}^\circ(i) - \Delta X_{i,d-id}^\circ(i) - \Delta X_{i,disp}^\circ(i) \quad (4)$$

when $X = G, S$ or H , and $i = TS$ or IS . Preliminary computations show that the contributions of $\Delta X_{i,d-id}^\circ(i)$ are fairly small compared to others and hence neglected. It was hoped that analysis of $\Delta X_{i,HH}^\circ(i)$ and particularly $T\Delta S_{i,HH}^\circ(i)$ -composition profiles, in terms of physicochemical properties and especially the structuredness of the solvents, is likely to help understand the observed minima in $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ and hence ΔH^\ddagger -composition profiles. So, $\Delta X_{i,cav}^\circ(i)$, $\Delta X_{i,dd}^\circ(i)$ and $\Delta X_{i,disp}^\circ(i)$ values were computed^{21-23b} by use of the appropriate formulations of scaled particle theory (SPT) of Keesom orientation expression and Karkwood-Muller formulae respectively, as given in literature²⁰ and in one of our

TABLE 5—VALUES (kJ mol⁻¹) OF ΔH_t^0 , $\Delta H_{t,cav}^0$, $\Delta H_{t,dd}^0$, $\Delta H_{t,disp}^0$, $\Delta H_{t,HH}^0$, ΔG_t^0 , ΔS_t^0 , $\Delta G_{t,HH}^0$, $T\Delta S_t^0$ FOR TRANSITION STATE (TS/MTS) OF t-BuCl IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT 298.15 K

Consol- vent wt%	Consol- vent mol ⁻¹	ΔH_t^0 (IS)	$\Delta H_{t,cav}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{t,dd}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{t,disp}^0$ (IS)	$\Delta H_{t,HH}^0$ (IS)	ΔG_t^0 (MIS)	$T\Delta S_t^0$ (TS)	$\Delta G_{t,HH}^0$ (MS)	$T\Delta S_t^0$ (TS)
TBA-H ₂ O										
10	2.6	-0.46	1.6	2.5	-3.8	-0.8	3.8	-4.3	7.6	-8.4
20	5.7	-16.33	5.7	5.7	-8.0	-19.7	(6.2)	-22.5	14.4	-34.1
30	9.6	-8.58	9.7	9.9	-12.2	-16.0	8.9	-17.5	17.4	-33.4
50	19.5	-4.05	9.6	22.0	-15.4	-20.3	16.1	-20.2	23.6	-43.9
EG-H ₂ O										
10	3.2	-10.33	1.2	2.6	-2.9	-11.2	5.0	-15.3	6.5	-17.7
30	11.0	-29.31	4.1	12.9	-8.3	-38.0	15.1	-44.4	16.2	-54.2
50	22.5	-11.70	7.3	35.2	-12.1	-42.1	31.2	-43.4	23.9	-66.0
ME-H ₂ O										
10	2.6	-38.74	3.1	2.7	-2.6	-41.9	9.3	-40.0	10.5	-52.4
30	9.2	-31.30	12.7	10.8	-6.4	-46.4	22.1	-53.4	19.3	-65.7
50	19.2	5.15	12.0	26.3	-10.5	-22.3	45.6	-40.4	41.3	-63.6
DME-H ₂ O										
10	2.2	-16.43	1.6	2.1	-3.4	-16.7	16.1	-32.5	19.6	-36.3
30	7.9	-21.41	6.3	8.1	-10.1	-25.7	40.5	-61.9	48.8	-74.5
50	16.7	-63.57	10.0	18.5	-15.2	-76.9	67.2	-130.8	75.8	-152.7
D-H ₂ O										
10	2.2	-40.69	3.2	0.2	-3.9	-40.2	9.9	-50.6	14.1	-54.3
30	8.1	-20.17	7.2	0.9	-12.2	-16.1	31.4	-51.6	44.4	-60.5
50	17.0	-27.76	7.7	1.9	-17.8	-19.6	42.6	-70.4	61.7	-81.3
DMSO-H ₂ O										
10	2.4	-21.56	-0.9	-17.4	-2.4	-0.9	-2.6	-19.0	8.0	-8.9
30	9.0	-15.48	5.0	-49.6	-7.6	36.7	-3.7	-11.8	23.9	12.8
50	18.7	-24.02	13.7	-66.5	-12.2	41.0	11.2	-35.2	44.0	-3.0
DMF-H ₂ O										
10	2.7	-5.37	2.6	-17.6	-3.0	12.6	1.5	-6.8	12.7	-0.1
30	9.5	-32.87	7.5	-43.6	-8.6	11.8	10.1	-42.9	36.3	-24.2
50	19.8	-23.36	16.4	-53.2	-13.8	27.2	43.6	-66.9	70.2	-43.0

$\Delta H_{t,HH}^0$ (TS) = ΔH_t^0 (TS) - $\Delta H_{t,cav}^0$ (TS) - $\Delta H_{t,dd}^0$ (TS) - $\Delta H_{t,disp}^0$ (TS), where TS = Bu^{δ+} ... Cl^{δ-} vide equation (3). The relevant parameters for computation of ΔH_t^0 (TS) terms for cavity, dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions as per equations in Refs. 20–23 and 25.

previous papers²⁵ and using the appropriate values of the required parameters from literature^{20,25,26} (vide Ref. 21). The values of the parameters so evolved are presented in Tables 2–5.

A perusal of the values of $\Delta G_{t,HH}^0$ of both IS and TS (vide Table 3 and also Figs. 3a and 3b) which are guided chiefly by the hydrophobic hydration (H_bH) of Me₃C^{δ+} group and hydrophilic hydration (H_lH) of hydrophilic Cl^{δ-} with $\delta_+ = \delta_- = 0.8^{27}$ in the case of TS and $\delta_+ = \delta_- = 0.2^{27}$ in the case of IS, suggests that both TS and IS are increasingly destabilised in all these aquo-organic mixtures as compared to water. And

as expected, different cosolvents reduce the composite HH interactions to different extents resulting in increased destabilisation of both TS and IS with the addition of cosolvents and the reduction for TS exceeding that for IS. And their order of reduction of HH-interaction^{23,28} is DME > D > DMF > DMSO > ME > TBA > EG in the case of TS, while DME > D > ME > TBA > EG > DMF > DMSO in the case of IS.

Figs. 4–10 present the composition profiles of ΔX_t^0 and $\Delta X_{t,HH}^0$ ($X = G, H$ or S) of both IS and TS of t-BuCl in the series of aqueous cosolvent

Fig. 3(a). Variation of (A) $\Delta G_{i,IS}^{\ddagger}$ and (B) $\Delta G_{i,HH}^{\ddagger}$ (IS) with mol % cosolvent in different aquo-organic solvents at 298.15 K.

systems. In view of the fact that behaviour of $T\Delta S_i^{\ddagger}$ and particularly $T\Delta S_{i,HH}^{\ddagger}$ of both IS and TS, are likely to help understand the behaviour of extrema $T\Delta S_i^{\ddagger}$ and hence ΔH_i^{\ddagger} , attempts have been made to understand the same for aqueous TBA and hence in other aquo-organic solvents in the light of Kundu *et al.*, is four-step transfer process^{24,28},

$$\Delta S_{i,HH}^{\ddagger}(i) = (\Delta S_1^{\ddagger} + \Delta S_2^{\ddagger}) + (\Delta S_3^{\ddagger} + \Delta S_4^{\ddagger}) \quad (5)$$

where ΔS_1^{\ddagger} is the entropy change accompanying the dismantling of the hydration sphere (hydrophobic and hydrophilic) round the $i = IS$ or TS ,

Fig. 4. Variation of transfer energetics $\Delta G_i^{\ddagger}, \Delta H_i^{\ddagger}, T\Delta S_i^{\ddagger}$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous t-butyl alcohol (TBA).

Fig. 3(b). Variation of (A) $\Delta G_{i,TS}^{\ddagger}$ (MST) and (B) $\Delta G_{i,HH}^{\ddagger}$ (MST) with mol % cosolvent in different aquo-organic solvents at 298.15 K.

ΔS_2^{\ddagger} is that accompanying the formation of 3D-water structure released from step 1, ΔS_3^{\ddagger} is that due to disruption of the structuredness of the cosolvents, if any, and ΔS_4^{\ddagger} is the entropy change associated with H_bH and H_iH interactions of the species in the aqueous cosolvents. The composite term $(\Delta S_1^{\ddagger} + \Delta S_2^{\ddagger})$ being related to water molecules remains constant for the respective species and is positive or negative depending upon the relative extents of the so-called primary solvation zone (psz) or the 'hydration cage' resulted from H_bH as well as H_iH interactions and the secondary solvation zone (ssz) past the hydration cage involved by the buffering action of psz and the normal water structure in the bulk. The other composite term $(\Delta S_3^{\ddagger} + \Delta S_4^{\ddagger})$ being related to the solvents, changes

Fig. 5. Variation of transfer energetics $\Delta G_i^{\ddagger}, \Delta H_i^{\ddagger}, T\Delta S_i^{\ddagger}$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol (ME).

Fig. 6 Variation of transfer energetics ΔG_t° , ΔH_t° , $T\Delta S_t^\circ$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixtures of 1,2-dimethoxy ethane (DME).

Fig. 8. Variation of transfer energetics ΔG_t° , ΔH_t° , $T\Delta S_t^\circ$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixture of dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO).

Fig. 7. Variation of transfer energetics ΔG_t° , ΔH_t° , $T\Delta S_t^\circ$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixtures of 1,4-dioxane (D).

Fig. 9 Variation of transfer energetics ΔG_t° , ΔH_t° , $T\Delta S_t^\circ$ (solid lines) and their corresponding HH interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixture of *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (DMF)

with cosolvent compositions and is dependent upon the relative structuredness of the solvating capacity of the solvent involved in steps 3 and 4 respectively.

In TBA-water mixtures in order to solvate the incoming species, IS or TS, the enhanced 3D-water structure caused by addition of TBA to water¹⁷, should be broken. As a result, the entropy change ΔS_3° should be a highly positive quantity. Also, as the species IS and TS are likely to induce less order due to less HH-interactions as compared to water, ΔS_4° should be less negative resulting in increasingly positive magnitudes of $(\Delta S_3^\circ + \Delta S_4^\circ)$ from the initial composition. But in view of the fact that $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ values of both the

species pass through a minimum (at lower compositions) it appears that at least a constant negative quantity is resulted from $(\Delta S_1^\circ + \Delta S_2^\circ)$ for any of the species. If we assume that H_bH -interaction causes the formation of psz around the three hydrophobic CH_3 groups, as is usually the case, the contribution $(\Delta S_1^\circ + \Delta S_2^\circ)$ will be a constant positive quantity, for the system changes from a more ordered (more H-bonding in the HH region) state (step 1) to a less ordered (normal/less H-bonded water) state (step 2). On the other hand, the water molecules in the ssz past the psz being in the disordered state (due to the $Cl^{\delta-}$ and the size factor of the H-bonded $(H_2O)_x$ cage around either of the species),

Fig. 10 Variation of transfer energetics ΔG_t° , ΔH_t° , $T\Delta S_t^\circ$ (solid lines) and their corresponding H1H interactions (dotted lines) of (A) initial state (IS) and (B) transition state (TS) of aqueous mixture of ethylene glycol.

the combined ($\Delta S_1^\circ + \Delta S_2^\circ$) would result in a constant negative quantity since the system changes from a less ordered (disordered water in ssz) state (step 1) to a more ordered (normal/more H-bonded water) one (step 2). Our present results, as in the case of R_4N^+ ions²⁸, particularly at lower TBA-compositions, show that the negative entropy (structural) effect of the ssz molecules overcome the negative entropy effect of HH of the species IS or TS contributing an overall constant negative magnitudes of ($\Delta S_1^\circ + \Delta S_2^\circ$). This when combined with the increasing positive magnitudes of ($\Delta S_3^\circ + \Delta S_4^\circ$) causes the minimum to occur as in Fig. 5. But beyond 6 mole % of TBA, breaking down of the relevant structures occurs due to the onset of packing imbalance^{28,29}.

Notably, the observed fairly more negative values of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ (TS) as compared with that of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ (IS) are indicative of the more ordering effect of highly polar TS over that of the faintly polar IS. Evidently, the corresponding behaviour of $\Delta H_{t,HH}^\circ$ (IS) and $\Delta H_{t,HH}^\circ$ (TS) and especially their roller-coaster behaviour are dictated by the respective $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ values.

If the above arguments be taken as plausible,

the observed increasingly negative values of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ -composition profiles of IS in aqueous mixtures of EG, ME and DME are seemingly the result of 3D-structure breaking effect of these organic cosolvents dictating $\Delta S_3^\circ \approx 0$ which was superimposed on the constant negative ($\Delta S_1^\circ + \Delta S_2^\circ$) terms and the increasingly negative ΔS_4° term. But the upward trend of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ -composition profile of TS at higher compositions of EG, is possibly due to the increased opposing action of H₁H interaction over H₆H interaction induced by the highly polar TS species, thus rendering $\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ value less negative. The observed upward trends, after passing through a minimum or hump in the case of ME and DME, might be adduced to the effect of possible H-bonded intercomponent complexes^{18h,j} and the terminal downward trends are the superimposed effect of packing imbalance, which makes $\Delta S_3^\circ = 0$ and ΔS_4° increasingly more negative.

In the case of D-water mixtures, the observed upward trends of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^\circ$ -composition profiles at higher compositions may be adduced to the superimposed increasing aproticity of D-water mixtures as induced by shifting of the possible chair-form to boat-form^{18i,22,23}. But the observed roller-coaster

behaviour of the said profile of the highly polar TS is possibly the resultant effects of TS-induced boat-form and the packing imbalance at higher compositions.

In DMF-water mixtures, the behaviour of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (IS)-composition profile is indicative of the effect of possible H-bonded intercomponent complexes^{18m}, which is likely to make $\Delta S_3^{\circ} \approx 0$, and thus to give rise to an upward trend at intermediate compositions, which is again seemingly overcome by the effect of packing imbalance at larger compositions. But the observed increasingly downward trend of $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ (TS) is the effect of largely negative dipole-dipole interaction term²⁷ over others making ΔS_4° term largely negative. This on subtraction from $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ (TS) values makes the $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (TS)-composition profile lie above the $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ (TS)-composition profile – a feature which is reverse to those observed in other cosolvent systems. The same is true for the relative positions of ΔH_t° (TS)- and $\Delta H_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (TS)-composition profiles.

In the case of DMSO-water mixtures, however, the behaviour of the $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ and $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ -composition profiles of IS is uniquely different from those in other cosolvent systems by exhibiting a maximum at initial compositions, instead of a minimum. Seemingly, this behaviour might be termed as a case of odd-man-out, as this might question the conjecture that $(\Delta S_2^{\circ} + \Delta S_3^{\circ})$ related to water is a negative quantity. But in view of the fact that $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ terms were obtained by subtracting $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ terms from the corresponding ΔH_t° terms, it might be true that the computation involved in finding out ΔG_t° (MTS) by adding interaction terms, especially $\Delta G_{t,dd}^{\circ}$ (i) and $\Delta G_{t,disp}^{\circ}$ (i), may be somewhat uncertain especially in this highly polar cosolvent system. This may ultimately give rise to the resulting small positive magnitudes to $T\Delta S_t^{\circ}$ and $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ terms for this solvent system.

Thus, it appears from the above-noted brief analysis

that the observed fairly more negative values of $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (TS) as compared to $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (IS) in most of the aquo-organic solvents, are indicative of more ordering effect of highly polar TS ($\mu = 8.5$ D)²⁷ over that of the feebly polar IS ($\mu = 2.5$ D)²⁷ and the superimposed structural effects of the mixed solvents that impart $\Delta S_3^{\circ} \approx 0$ in the case of 3D-structure breaking solvents or $\Delta S_3^{\circ} > 0$ in the case of cosolvents with intercomponent H-bonded complexes, which partly caused the observed roller-coaster behaviour in some cases. Evidently, the corresponding behaviour of $\Delta H_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (IS) and $\Delta H_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ (TS) and especially their roller-coaster behaviour are dictated by the respective $T\Delta S_{t,HH}^{\circ}$ values. And the resultant effects are seemingly responsible for the observed minima in $T\Delta S^{\circ}$ and hence for the observed unique endothermic minima in all the aquo-organic solvents, which proved baffling, so to say, since the days of classical work of Ingold and Hughes³⁰ on this key S_N1 -type reaction.

References

1. C. REICHARDT, (a) *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1965, **4**, 29; (b) 1979, **18**, 98; (c) *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, **58**, 1857.
2. I. A. KOPPEL and V. A. PALM, "Advances in Linear Free Energy Relationship", Plenum, New York, 1972.
3. M. H. ABRAHAM, (a) *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1985, **59**, 1055 and relevant references therein; (b) M. H. ABRAHAM, P. L. GRELLIER, A. NASZEDEH and R. A. C. WALKER, *J. Chem. Soc., Parkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 1717 and relevant references therein.
4. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, "Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1963.
5. E. M. ARNETT, W. C. BENTRUDE, J. J. BURKE and P. J. DUGGLEBY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1541.
6. M. H. ABRAHAM, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **11**, 1.
7. A. J. PARKER, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 173; *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 1; R. A. ALEXANDER, A. J. PARKER and T. BROXTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **90**, 5049.
8. (a) M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *J. Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 55; (b) M. J. BLANDMER, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **14**, 203; (c) M. J. BLANDMER, J. M. W. SCOTT and R. E. ROBERTSON, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **15**, 150.
9. (a) J. B. F. N. ENGBERTS in "Water : A Comprehensive Treatise", ed. F. FRANKS, Plenum, New York, Vol. 6, 1976; (b) *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, **54**, 1947.
10. Y. KONDO, M. ITTON and SUSABAYESHI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1982, **78**, 3793.
11. A. J. PARKER, D. MAYER, R. SCHIMD and V. GUTMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 1843.

12. U. MANDAL, S. SEN, K. DAS and K. K. KUNDU, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1986, **64**, 300, 1638.
13. E. BUNCCEL and C. WILSON, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1979, **12**, 42.
14. (a) S. WINSTEIN, E. GRUWAID and H. W. JONES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2700; (b) S. WINSTEIN, A. H. FAINBERG and S. WINSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1608, 4116; (c) A. H. FAINBERG and S. WINSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2770; (d) S. W. WINSTEIN and A. H. FAINBERG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 5957.
15. R. E. ROBERTSON and S. E. SUGAMRI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 7254; *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 1353 and the relevant references therein.
16. R. HUQ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1973, **69**, 1195.
17. F. FRANKS and D. J. G. IVES, *Quart. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 20.
18. K. K. KUNDU and coworkers, (a) *Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, **13**, 95; (b) *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1978, **74**, 1054; (c) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 961; (d) 1981, **59**, 3149; (e) 1989, **67**, 315; (f) 1983, **61**, 625; (g) *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 4055; (h) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1981, **59**, 3149, 3141; (i) *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 9; (j) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1985, **63**, 798, 806; (k) *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 347; (l) 1981, **20**, 253; (m) *Electrochim. Acta*, 1981, **26**, 479; (n) *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, **70**, 1452; (o) *J. Solution Chem.*, 1979, **8**, 299; (p) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1980, **58**, 79; (q) *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 467 and the relevant references therein.
19. B. G. COX, G. R. HEDWIG, A. J. PARKER and D. W. WATTA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, **27**, 477.
20. Y. MARCUS, "Ion-Solvation", Willey, Chichester, 1985.
21. M. DATTA (née SARKAR), Ph.D. Thesis, Jadavpur University, 1992.
22. M. DATTA (née SARKAR), M. L. DAS, J. DATTA and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 472.
23. (a) M. DATTA (née SARKAR) and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 478; (b) unpublished results.
24. R. W. TAFT, M. H. ABRAHAM, R. M. DOHERTY and M. J. KAMLET, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 3185.
25. (a) S. SINHA, S. P. RUDRA and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 1; (b) S. SINHA and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 12.
26. S. P. RUDRA, B. P. CHAKRAVARTY, K. K. KUNDU and I. N. BASUMULLICK, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1986, **150**, 211.
27. M. H. ABRAHAM, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1972, 1343.
28. H. TALUKDER and K. K. KUNDU, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 3796; 1992, **96**, 1970.
29. K. K. KUNDU and coworkers, (a) *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 303; (b) *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1978, **74**, 1051 and the relevant references therein; (c) *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 961; (d) 1981, **59**, 3149, 3141; (e) 1985, **63**, 798, 806.
30. E. D. HUGHES and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 244.